

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ATTA****FIRST NAME: AMINA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing a good academic discussion (EUCLID 2024, 7-13)
2. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 25-28)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34-38)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 41-42)
5. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2024, 44-50)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

When I initially laid my hands on the materials made available to me by EUCLID University, especially the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D, I was lost because little did I know that it was material to comprehend. Reading through the material, I became more confused because I saw guidelines for writing a good academic essay, punctuation, et cetera. (EUCLID 2024, 7-15). Upon watching the attached video, I learned that it was all about tracking changes when reviewing a paper using Microsoft Office Word. This further confused me since this is something I already knew.

However, on second thought, I carefully read through the course pack. Further, I watched the video again and again when I learned that I needed to write an open response paper on the available materials given to me. I, therefore, understood that there is always room for learning again and again and again. Then, I took my time to comprehend all the sections on essay writing, punctuations, American and British English, plagiarism, style guide, the Chicago style, Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2024, 7-70), and the last section on sample correction to papers. This gave me an understanding that an academic essay is different from others for its guided rules, including in-text citations and

a list of references for acknowledgment and to avoid plagiarism. The writing style and type of English used also matter to avoid irrelevant mistakes.

Based on my understanding of the study materials, I intend to provide my discussion under the following headings: essay writing, American vs British English, plagiarism, style guide, and CMS crib sheet while reviewing an academic essay.

2) ESSAY WRITING

To write an academic essay, I learned from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period one (1) chapter one that it requires a careful plan that includes a proper understanding of the question to answer by the essay, proper literature review of relevant materials and jotting down points, and then develop the ideas obtained while arranging the literature into planned sections of the writeup. Then, it will be followed by drafting the sections of the essay, i.e., the introduction, the body, which is made of several sections depending on the nature of the essay question, and then the concluding part (EUCLID 2024, 7-8).

I also understand that while reviewing the literature, one is expected to apply previous knowledge of the question and to always keep the question to be answered in mind at all times. This is relevant as it will keep guiding one on what information to focus on, what material is relevant to the question, and which one speaks to the question directly without taking too much time. The literature search should be widely sought, including online material, i.e., e-books, journal articles, reviews by other authors, and even editorials of publishers. Materials should also be sought from physical textbooks, journals, periodicals, et cetera. These should help one get sound evidence, such as case studies, statistics, and important quotes to support one's arguments (EUCLID 2024, 8-9).

One needs to apply creativity and critical thinking in essay writing. This could help broaden the ideas gathered during the literature search and, at the same time, help to narrow the scope of the essay. It also helps in the critical evaluation of different arguments, including those in support of your ideas and those with different views. The ideas gathered can then be organized into which are useful to answer the questions, which to write first and last, in which order these ideas should be, and what examples or evidence to include (EUCLID 2024, 9-10).

After that, one is expected to come up with a draft of the essay written using the ideas gathered during the literature search in the chosen structure. This may be just the introduction, body, and conclusion, or one in which the body is further separated into sub-headings, as the case may be. Each paragraph is expected to deal with mainly a point with clarity. After stating each point, supporting sentences further expatiate and make it clearer for better understanding, especially when proper examples or statistics are given as evidence. These evidence and points given must be acknowledged by clear intext referencing and prevent plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 10-11).

One can then start editing his/her draft gradually before finally coming up with a final draft of the essay he/she intends to produce. Editing will always make the essay better than the initial draft because each time you revisit it, you come up with fresh and better ideas and more information to finetune the earlier ones. Then you hand in the essay, and before that, you should revisit the guidelines initially provided for writing the essay and comply with the due date for submission, the format of submission preferred by the course tutor, and the right place to submit it. Some rules of thumb were also given at the end of this section in the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack EUCLID 2024, 11-13).

3) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I learned from Chapter Three that, firstly, Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) are similar regional languages that have attained significant global usage since World War II. Secondly, the SAE has exponentially dominated international language usage over British English (SBE) due to its “political, economic, technological advancement and cultural values”. American and British English are both said to be similar variants, with linguistic differences attributed to variations in history, societal values, and cultural trends (EUCLID 2024, 25).

I understand from this reading that the difference between American and British English evolved as a result of vocabulary dialect or localism across the nations. The most significant aspect discussed in this chapter is the language differences, which span variations in pronunciation, spelling, grammar, syntax, and vocabulary, including variations in collective nouns, pluralized adjectives, and common phrases, all validating the evolution and shift in vocabulary. The given examples in the course pack explain the variation in pronunciation and spellings in some words; for instance, “Renaissance and clerk” – have the same spelling but are pronounced differently in both vocabularies. One should also take note of other words that have different spelling but the same pronunciation, for example, “color and colour; aging and ageing” as seen in SAE and SBE (EUCLID 2024, 26-27).

In addition, I learned that some words are shown to be different but have similar pronunciation and spelling (for example, rise verse raise), and others have the same words but different meanings (maize versus sweet corn). There is also the question of pluralization of adjectives in SBE compared to SAE in many cases due to individual usage of idioms. I observed many highlighted vocabulary usage differences and some words with the same concepts, which are expressed differently, as seen in the words – petrol versus gasoline and public holiday versus bank holiday (EUCLID 2024, 28), et cetera. One should note other differences in equality vocabulary (i.e. fireman versus firefighter; chairman versus chairperson), politically correct references (Seniors versus Elderly; housewife versus stay-at-home-mom, et cetera.), regional variation in terms such as Soda versus Pop versus Coke; Uncle Sam versus John Bull, et cetera., It is quite interesting to note that there is also a difference in obscenities, punctuation and dates, and punctuations in formal and information letters in both standard English languages.

The ACA-401D period one-course pack gives me clarity on the English version that should be used for EUCLID academic writing. Although it is clearly noted that SAE and SBE, while exhibiting significant variations, remain mutually intelligible, its usage in academic papers should be limited to one or the other.

4) PLAGIARISM

The ACA-401D coursework period one (1) chapter four provides a comprehensive overview of plagiarism, emphasizing its ethical implications and the necessity of proper attribution in academic writing. According to this reading, "the unauthorized use of another scholar's work, whether by paraphrasing or reproduction of any part without giving proper credit, is considered a breach of academic principle and undermines scholarly credibility" (EUCLID 2024, 34). From the chapter, I gained insights into key elements of plagiarism, including proper attribution, source acknowledgment, citation methods, formatting conventions, and footnote referencing.

According to the chapter, one needs to correctly attribute an author's ideas—whether through direct quotations, paraphrasing, statistical data, or other referenced material—is fundamental to maintaining academic integrity. It is imperative to always give proper citations. One should be aware that proper citation not only ensures due credit to original authors but also mitigates risks of intellectual property infringement and ethical misconduct. In addition, the chapter further convinces me that exploring various citation approaches, such as in-text citations, direct quotations, adhering to standardized formatting rules, and ensuring accurate paraphrasing helps to preserve the original meaning and scholarly value (EUCLID 2024, 34-36).

Moreover, I have noted that the use of signal phrases—such as "point out"—allows for integrating an author's name at the beginning of a sentence as documented by Gerson and Gerson before 1984 is still correct" (EUCLID 2024, 143). While adherence to citation rules is crucial, one has to understand equally when citations are unnecessary. I have learned that common and widely accepted factual information does not require citation as they are common knowledge or information, thereby ensuring efficiency and clarity in one's academic writing (EUCLID 2024, 37-38).

5) STYLE GUIDE

Chapter five of the ACA-401D course pack period one (1), provides clear guidance on how to format Euclid paper, the most preferred use of the English language, and a style guide, which all serve as an essential tool in ensuring consistency and coherence in writing, particularly in professional and technical contexts. The narrative highlights the importance of style guides across different writing structures, from academic to business communication to journalism and web content. I learned that it is necessary to conform to uniformity when several researchers or writers provide input in a single publication; this will ensure that one's personal writing styles do not overshadow the brand, organization,

or intended message. Hence, one can note that consistency and uniformity are important when writing for academic purposes (EUCLID 2024, 41)

Considering that my country of residence is in West Africa, and writing guides require one to conform to the historical and idiom using British English, this chapter convinced me that all writing on this course should adhere to the EUCLID standardized style guide. Consequently, I have noted all academic writers from EUCLID, for example, are expected to rely on approved style guides, Chicago Rules (Turabian), America English, and EUCLID template to meet academic writing expectations and maintain consistency across documents (EUCLID 2024, 41-42).

One of the most compelling aspects of the discussion is the emphasis on freelance writers and in-house writers, a topic I have a personal interest in. One can clearly understand that both writers are employed differently, as a result of which the freelancers may need to adhere to a prescribed style, and developing personalized guides based on client preferences can enhance client satisfaction and build long-term relationships. I have learned that adaptability is crucial in competitive writing markets (EUCLID 2024, 42).

6) CMS CRIB SHEET

One choice to write on a CMS crib sheet as I have never heard of this before, and I believe this is an excellent time to understand the Chicago style as documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) for academic writers. From this reading, I have learned that the Chicago style is applied to all research papers, and the form of concept, from the style usage to page formatting to Chicago endnote and footnote, should be strictly adhered to (EUCLID 2024, 44).

I understand that one needs to be careful to monitor abbreviations as they are used sparsely and only when they are easily clear to readers. When writing academic papers, one should understand that abbreviations- unlikely acronyms- are mostly seen in tables or references and rarely in text. The overview explains the three forms of capitalization and when to use the full, headings, and sentence caps in books, articles, ethnic groups, geographical names, and other terminologies. As a result, one needs to understand when to provide these forms when writing an academic paper (EUCLID 2024,44-45).

I learned that compound words are majorly hyphenated so as not to alter their meanings. This should be differentiated from conditional compound words, which change based on usage (EUCLID 2024, 46).

The readings are quite detailed and comprehensive, and one must take time to read and note all sections to have a clear understanding of academic writing requirements. Also, following the guidelines for the Chicago style sheet enhances readability and ensures well-structured, professional academic writing that meets standards. I acknowledge that mastering these rules will enhance my professional writing skills' effectiveness and prevent inaccuracy (EUCLID 2024, 50).

7) CONCLUSION

I am optimistic that delivering my first response paper for the AC-401D course pack, along with taking time to engage with the videos and course orientation materials, marks a strong beginning for both my academic writing journey and my PhD in Global Health and Health Systems.

Initially, opening the course pack made me realize how much I need to relearn and unlearn. I felt lost, unsure of where to begin or how to approach the assignment. Having been away from academic writing for some time, I recognize that if I must scale this hurdle, it is essential that I adhere to all instructions and guidelines provided. Watching Dr. Gulma's YouTube sample review video provided clarity and assurance that I can provide a passable response paper as well. I am hopeful of becoming better committed to refining my writing skills and becoming an effective and creative professional writer. I understand that to achieve this, I must strictly follow the guidelines and styles for academic writing. It may require intentional learning, re-editing, and review, but this is what I have signed up for.

Moving forward, this course pack will serve as my essential guide, helping me navigate and excel in this academic endeavor.

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